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Accessibility and Transportation Systems Planning: A Literature Review.

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Abstract

The scientific literature evidences a considerable proliferation of theoretical definitions and accessibility measurement methodologies, as well as research on their incorporation into transportation systems planning, concentrated predominantly in European and North American contexts, while Latin America presents significantly limited representation. This article develops a systematic literature review aimed at examining the integration of accessibility instruments in urban transportation systems planning. The methodology employed was based on the Scopus database, delimiting the analysis to scientific publications from the last fifteen years. An exhaustive bibliometric analysis was executed that included the evaluation of main authors, identification of keyword frequencies through VOSviewer software, and thematic content analysis. The results initially identified 14 articles of greatest academic relevance, from which 41 variables were extracted and categorized into nine fundamental analytical dimensions: socioeconomic, active mobility, public transport, automobile use, other transport modes, transport-related information, general information, health, and institutional information. These categories constitute an operational conceptual framework that can be employed in the design of research instruments to diagnose accessibility in transportation systems planning in emerging urban contexts.

Keywords: Accessibility, Transportation, Planning, Process, Strategies.

1. Introduction

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In the contemporary urban context, the problems associated with transportation constitute one of the most significant challenges derived from the accelerated growth of metropolitan areas. The authorities responsible for the management of public transport face the imperative of ensuring sufficient operational capacity to meet the exponential increase in the demand for travel in urban areas (Papa et al., 2015). This increase, generated mainly by individual motorized trips, generates multidimensional impacts on the quality of life of the population and economic productivity. Transportation costs cause economic, social, and environmental losses, and also have a high impact on territorial configuration (Bertolini et al., 2005). Faced with this problem, public managers have developed transport management and planning policies that broaden their focus to the poles that generate trips and the opportunities offered by the city, such as employment centers, health services, educational institutions and recreational spaces.

The academic literature on accessibility, its taxonomy, and associated measures and indicators is extensive (Geurs & Van Wee, 2004). Various studies address the issue of planning and support for different urban planning objectives. This document aims to provide knowledge around the following research question: How does accessibility contribute to the planning of transport systems? To answer this question, the document is based on the results of an exhaustive bibliometric analysis, examining the state of the art regarding accessibility and the planning of transport systems at a global level.

Accessibility tools are a specific type of planning support systems designed to support the analysis and integrated planning of transport and land use, providing explicit knowledge about the accessibility of different modes of transport at different geographical scales (Silva & Pinho, 2010). These instruments measure, interpret, and model accessibility, developing to support the many analytical tasks involved in planning practice (Bertolini, 2012). Accessibility and its analysis offer an appropriate conceptual framework to support the development of combined strategies in transport planning, in order to achieve the coordination and symbiosis necessary to achieve urban sustainability objectives (Holden, 2012).

The accessibility-centred approach makes explicit the overall objective of the integrated land use and transport system, establishing a direct link between the characteristics of mobility flows (travel speeds and times) and the characteristics of places (opportunities offered by each urban sector). Due to these characteristics, it represents a differentiated approach for planning professionals, who

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can use it to develop and evaluate effective strategies aimed at sustainable cities (Straatemeier, 2008), allowing urban planning and transport to be acted upon and coordinated more efficiently through the prism of accessibility.

Therefore, this article aims to identify in the international literature the variables that influence the way in which accessibility has been used in the planning of transport systems, through a systematic bibliometric review. The article is structured in four sections: the introduction in section 1; the methodology in section 2; the results and analyses in section 3; and the conclusions in section 4.

2. Methodology

To carry out the study, two main methodological stages were defined. The first stage corresponds to the systematic collection of information through a bibliometric study that included the methods of data collection and selection of academic publications. The second stage defines the analysis and interpretation of the results obtained.

1.1 Information Collection

The Scopus database was selected as the primary source for the identification of relevant scientific articles. According to Elsevier (2019), this platform constitutes the largest database of abstracts and citations of peer-reviewed literature currently available, guaranteeing the quality and academic rigor of the publications. The search terms were defined in English, considering that it is the predominant language in the Scopus database and in international scientific production.

Initially, the appropriate keywords for the proposed analysis were established, based on scientific studies published in recent years. The applicable terms are presented in Table 1.

Keyword	Keywords
Accessibility	Accessibility
Transportation	Transportation / Transport
Planning	Planning / Planning process / Planning strategies
Urban	Urban
America	America

Table 1. Defined words for the delimitation of scientific productions

Based on these terms, the bibliographic search expression was constructed using the content of titles, abstracts or keywords of the studies. The search expression was structured using the Boolean operator "AND" as follows: Accessibility AND Transportation AND planning process AND urban AND america.

The initial search was carried out in the Scopus reference database, obtaining 10 results. When refining the results by country/territory, one article was identified from Mexico, three from the United States, three from the Netherlands, one from Korea, and two undefined articles. When the visualization map was subsequently verified, it was evident that in Latin America the studies associated with these search variables are significantly limited, which is why it was decided to analyze the results at a global level.

Several search scenarios were proposed to expand the sample. The expression Accessibility AND Transportation AND planning generated 2,438 results. The expression Accessibility AND Transportation AND planning process produced 683 results. Finally, the most specific expression was used: Accessibility AND Transport system AND planning process AND urban AND strategies, executed on July 10, 2021, obtaining 23 results.

Based on these results, three methodological filters were applied for the refinement of the sample. Initially, only publications made in the last 15 years (2007 to 2021) were considered, which comprise approximately 86% of the identified works. Subsequently, in order to guarantee the academic quality of the papers, only the documents classified in the categories of scientific article and academic review were selected. Finally, the abstracts were read and critically analyzed for the final selection of publications that were consistent with the theme of accessibility and transport planning. At the conclusion of the methodological refinement, 14 articles were considered for exhaustive analysis (Figure 1).

Search Results Refinement Process

Figure 1. Refinement of publications obtained through methodological filters

2. Results and analysis

The application of the search protocols using the methods described above was executed in the Scopus database, initially identifying 23 articles. After a critical reading of the abstract of each article and considering the temporal criterion of the last 15 years, nine publications whose thematic contents were outside the scope of this work were excluded, resulting in the selection of 14 publications. Of these, 85.7% correspond to scientific articles and 14.3% to academic reviews and conference proceedings (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Documents by type

The selected articles cover the period from 2007 to 2021. In the temporal analysis, it was observed that from 2012 the number of citations began to increase, reaching 6 citations. During the period 2016, 20 citations were registered, subsequently increasing to reach 39 citations in 2020. In this way, the sustained growth of the topic associated with accessibility and planning of transport systems is remarkable, with the highest cumulative number of citations with a total of 42 citations in 2021 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Citations in the period considered between 2007-2021

The oldest article dates from 2007, authored by Cheng, Bertolini and Le Clercq (2007), published in Transportation Research Record, constituting one of the most cited with 38 citations in Scopus. Also noteworthy are the works of Su et al. (2014), entitled "A land use and transportation integration method for land use allocation and transportation strategies in China", with 16 citations, and Shiau (2013), "Evaluating sustainable transport strategies for the counties of Taiwan based on their degree of urbanization", with 12 citations. Table 2 presents the complete distribution of citations of the 14 documents analyzed.

Table 2. Citations per Analyzed Document (2007–2021)

Totals — <2017: 55 | 2017: 22 | 2018: 34 | 2019: 24 | 2020: 39 | 2021: 29 | Subtotal: 148 | >2021: 0 | Total: 203

#	Documents	Year	<2017	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Subtotal	>2021	Total
1	Multi-criteria approach for prioritizing and managing public...	2021									
2	A proposal to compare urban infrastructure using multi-crite...	2021									
3	How can planning for accessibility lead to more integrated t...	2020						5	5		5
4	Transit oriented development among metro station areas in Sh...	2019				4	13	10	27		27
5	The TUM Accessibility Atlas as a tool for supporting policie...	2017		1	3	1	3		8		8
6	Analysing stakeholders' perception of Light Rail Transit as...	2016		3	1	2	1		7		7
7	A land use and transportation integration method for...	2014	3	1	2	4	3	3	13		16
8	IFIP WG 5.7 International Conference on Advances in Products...	2014				1			1		1
9	Evaluating sustainable transport strategies for the counties...	2013	3	2	4		2	1	9		12
10	Spatial impacts of high-speed railways in China: A total-tra...	2013	4	3	10	5	11	7	36		40
11	51st Annual Transportation Research Forum 2010	2010									
12	Integrated housing service for Australians in later life	2010	2	2	1	1		1	5		7
13	Decision-making for light rail	2009	26	4	6	1	3	2	16		42
14	Measuring sustainable accessibility	2007	17	6	7	5	3		21		38

Table 2. Citations for each document

The authors who present the most scientific production on the subject in this database are Bertolini, L., who specializes in the measurement of sustainable accessibility and how accessibility planning can lead to more integrated transport and land use strategies, and Villegas Flores, N., who develops multi-criteria approaches to manage and prioritize public investment in urban spaces, each with 2 publications in Scopus (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Documents by author

It was also verified, in the selected articles, that countries such as China, the Netherlands, Brazil and the United Kingdom were the most promising in the development of issues related to accessibility and planning of transport systems

Figure 5. Documents by country or territory

Regarding the bibliometric networks, the VOSviewer software was used to construct and visualize the co-occurrence relationships (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010) of all the articles selected by keywords. Figure 6 presents the visualization map of the bibliometric network of co-occurrence by keywords in Scopus. The relationship between accessibility, accessibility instruments, transport planning, urban planning, sustainable development and transport policies are strongly interrelated in the articles analyzed, evidencing clearly defined thematic clusters.

Figure 6. VOSviewer Keywords Display

Once the quantitative bibliometric analysis was carried out, a qualitative content analysis of each article was carried out to identify and systematize its main characteristics. Table 3 presents the systematization of the content of the 14 selected articles, including the title, year of publication, authors, source of publication and number of citations registered.

#	Title	Year	Authors	Source	Cited by
1	Multi-criteria approach for prioritizing and managing public investment in urban spaces. A case study in the triple frontier	2021	Villegas Flores, N., Saldeño Madero, Y., Torres Parra, C.A., Fasolino, I., Rondón Quintana, H.A.	Sustainability 13(6), 3345	0
2	A proposal to compare urban infrastructure using multi-criteria analysis	2021	Villegas Flores, N., Cruz Salvador, L.C., Parapinski, A.C., Madero, Y.S.	Land Use Policy	0
3	How can planning for accessibility lead to more integrated transport and land-use strategies?	2020	Straatemeier, T., Bertolini, L.	European Planning Studies 28(9), pp. 1713–1734	5
4	Transit oriented development among metro station areas in Shanghai, China	2019	Li, Z., Han, Z., Xin, J., (...), Su, S., Weng, M.	Land Use Policy 82, pp. 269–282	27
5	The TUM Accessibility Atlas as a tool for supporting sustainable mobility policies	2017	Wulfhorst, G., Büttner, B., Ji, C.	Transport. Research Part A 104, pp. 121–136	8
6	Analysing stakeholders' perception of Light Rail Transit for sustainable mobility in Granada	2016	Valenzuela-Montes, L.M., Soria-Lara, J.A., Navarro-Ligero, M.L.	Journal of Transport Geography 54, pp. 391–399	7
7	A land use and transportation integration method for land use allocation in China	2014	Su, H., Wu, J.H., Tan, Y., (...), Song, B., El, X.	Transport. Research Part A 69, pp. 329–353	16
8	IFIP WG 5.7 Intl. Conference on Advances in Production Management Systems, APMS 2014	2014	[No author available]	IFIP Advances in ICT 439(PART 2)	1
9	Evaluating sustainable transport strategies for Taiwan counties by degree of urbanization	2013	Shiau, T.-A.	Transport Policy 30, pp. 101–108	12
10	Spatial impacts of high-speed railways in China: A total-travel-time approach	2013	Wang, J.J., Xu, J., He, J.	Environment and Planning A 45(9), pp. 2261–2280	40
11	51st Annual Transportation Research Forum 2010	2010	[No author available]	51st Annual Transport. Research Forum 2010	0
12	Integrated housing service for Australians in later life	2010	Jones, A., Howe, A., Tilse, C., Bartlett, H., Stimson, B.	AHURI Final Report (141), pp. 1–169	7
13	Decision-making for light rail	2009	De Bruijn, H., Veeneman, W.	Transport. Research Part A 43(4), pp. 349–359	42
14	Measuring sustainable accessibility	2007	Cheng, J., Bertolini, L., Le Clercq, F.	Transport. Research Record (2017), pp. 16–25	38

Table 3. Systematization of the information of the selected documents

Once the 14 research documents were identified and their compatibility with the theme of accessibility and planning of transport systems was verified, the variables used in the studies were systematically extracted. As a result, 41 variables were identified that have been used to study the accessibility and planning of transport systems, either in direct aspects such as the improvement of transport, or in their effects in the context of sustainable cities. Table 4 presents the 41 variables with the frequency of citation of the authors, which for methodological convenience were coded from 1 to 14, whose identifiers correspond to the 14 documents considered for the analysis of the bibliographic review.

The 41 variables were grouped into thematic categories related to their affinity of representation and function with respect to accessibility and transport planning, as verified in the literature of the 14 selected articles. In this way, nine (9) fundamental categories were established: (1) socioeconomic; (2) active mobility; (3) public transportation; (4) use of automobile; (5) other modes of transportation; (6) transportation-related information; (7) general information; (8) health; and (9) information on institutions.

Table 4 shows that variables such as "gender" and "age" are mentioned by 12 and 11 authors, respectively, which shows their relevance in most of the studies analyzed. In the category of active mobility, the most cited variables are "accessibility" and "cycling", with 14 and 10 authors respectively. In the public transport category, "collective public transport" was mentioned by 9 authors and "public transport stop" by 5 authors. In the remaining categories, the variable "train/metro" stands out with 5 authors in the category of other modes. In the category of transport-related information, 7 authors mentioned "trip duration". In the general information category, 8 authors refer to the variable "climate". In the health category, 4 authors mention the variable "health", and in the category of information on institution, 6 authors mention the variable "public".

Category	Variable	Authors	Total
Socioeconomic	Gender	1,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,14	12
	Age	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11	11
	Residence	2,8,11,13,14	5
	Education level	2,8,11	3
	Resources	1,8,11	3
	Investment	1,3,6	3
	Production	7,8	2
	Planning	3,4	2
	Origin and destination	1,3,4	3
	Destinations	1	1
Active Mobility	Accessibility	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14	14
	Cycling	2,3,4,6,7,8,9,11,13,14	10
	Mobility	3,4,7,8,11	5
	Bike lane	8,11	2
	Street	1,8,11	3
Public Transport	Collective public transport	1,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11	9
	Public transport stop	1,4,6,8,11	5
	Infrastructure	1,2	2
	Policy	5	1
	Transport cost	4	1
	Train / Metro	4,6,8,10,13	5
Automobile Use	Automobile use	8,11	2
	Car ownership	4,8,10	3
Other Modes	Motorcycle	8,9,11	3
	Other	4,6,8,10,11	5
Transport-related Info	Trip duration	1,3,5,6,8,10,11	7
	Travel mode	4,6,8,11	4
	Land use	4,7	2
	Speed	10	1
General Information	Climate	1,2,3,4,6,7,8,11	8
	Environment	5,6	2
	Sustainable	8,9,14	3
	Urban	1,2	2
	Works	1	1
	Housing	12	1
Health	Health	2,4,8,11	4
	Reduced mobility	1	1
	Special needs	8,11	2
	Physical activities	8	1
Institutional Info	Public	1,8,4,6,7,11	6
	Private	2,4,8	3

Table 4. Variables that relate accessibility to transport planning

3. Conclusions

The objective of this article was to conduct a systematic literature review to identify how accessibility contributes to the planning of transport systems, by identifying the main factors based on research indexed in the Scopus database.

From the documents analyzed, 14 scientific articles were selected that address accessibility and the planning of transport systems, in which, based on the existing opportunities in urban centers, effective public transport policies can be generated. In these studies, the urban transport network <https://analysisandmetaphysics.com/>

is oriented towards accessibility and the places where the activities of people who live and work in a city take place.

The planning process involves people's access to the opportunities offered by the city. Accessibility incorporates a differentiated way of measuring the quality of the transport system under metrics other than traditional ones, and is transversal in the studies considered. This dimension is significantly linked to variables such as gender, public transport, travel time, climate and health, evidencing its multidimensional nature and its potential as an integrating tool in urban planning.

The accessibility instruments identified in this review are fundamental tools for the development of integrated transport and land use planning strategies. The systematization of 41 variables into nine categories provides a robust conceptual framework that can be used by researchers and practitioners to diagnose and evaluate accessibility in diverse urban contexts, particularly in Latin America, where scientific production on this topic still presents significant opportunities for development.

Bibliometric evidence demonstrates a sustained growth in academic interest in the integration of accessibility in the planning of transport systems, especially since 2012. This increase reflects the growing recognition of accessibility as a fundamental paradigm for achieving objectives of urban sustainability, social equity and efficiency in mobility. Future research could focus on the empirical application of these instruments in Latin American cities, considering their socioeconomic, institutional and territorial particularities.

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